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NAVIGATING SKILLS AND DECENT WORK UNDER TECHNOLOGICAL CHANGE: THE CASE OF UKRAINIAN MIGRANTS IN THE EU

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Abstract. The outbreak of full-scale war in Ukraine in 2022 has led to an unprecedented wave of forced migration to European countries, where the activation of the Temporary Protection Directive has granted Ukrainian migrants’ immediate access to the labor markets of host countries.

European labor markets are currently characterized by labor shortages. Labor market fragmentation and persistent gaps in working conditions between local and migrant workers remain significant. This study investigates whether early integration of Ukrainian migrants perpetuates the skills gap, especially in the context of technological change. It also examines whether there are differences across European countries in improving migrant working conditions and upholding decent work standards while addressing labor market challenges. The analysis builds on recent research that highlights the importance of early labor market integration, host country acquisition of human capital, and targeted policy interventions to support win-win outcomes for both migrants and host countries.

This study is based on a survey of 214 Ukrainian migrants in three EU countries—the Netherlands, Germany, and Poland. The latter two have hosted the largest numbers of Ukrainians under temporary protection (about 1 million or more in each of them at different times during 2022–2025), though some part of Ukrainian migrants in all three countries arrived prior to the full-scale invasion. The survey questions relate to decent work standards for migrants, skill mismatches, employment status downgrading, and inequalities faced by Ukrainian migrants compared to local workers and other migrant groups. Certain questions also address aspects of remote work and employment through digital platforms and how these may contribute to labor market fragmentation in times of technological change. The non-probability survey data was analyzed with non-parametric tests (Kruskal–Wallis, Brunner–Munzel with Holm’s correction, and effect sizes) to assess differences between country groups. The analysis highlights cross-country differences in decent work opportunities for Ukrainians, with Poland and the Netherlands offering more flexibility in work schedules, better career prospects, and greater access to benefits compared to Germany, while differences in unpaid overtime were less pronounced. More regulated labor markets, while offering stronger social protection, pose greater adaptation challenges for migrants, mainly due to language barriers. Poland’s less regulated system facilitates quicker integration, though often through informal employment, and across countries, migrants with higher education levels retain better professional continuity than those with only bachelor’s degrees or none.

The institutionalization of skill navigation pathways for better job matching, access to retraining and micro-qualification services, and the reduction of regulatory barriers to migrant employment could

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help overcome local labor market deficits and improve decent work for migrants amid ongoing technological changes.

Keywords: decent work, migration, skills navigation, Ukrainians, co-determination.

Introduction

Decent work as a fundamental component of the 8th Sustainable Development Goal and as a core concept of the International Labour Organization (ILO) is intended to improve the working lives of all workers without exception, regardless of gender (European Commission, 2025), racial or national affiliation, or migration background. However, migrants remain among the most vulnerable groups, often engaged in precarious employment with low standards that fall short of the dignity of work (Mallett, 2018). There is a persistent link between migrant labor, particularly that of newly arrived migrants, and low job quality (Wright & Clibborn, 2019).

Decent work for migrants has remained a priority of international organizations for more than a decade, precisely because of the persistent challenges in achieving this objective. In 2014, the ILO adopted the Fair Migration Agenda—a framework launched to promote migration as an informed choice rather than a necessity, by fostering decent work in countries of origin and ensuring the protection of human rights, labor rights, and fair recruitment practices for all migrants.

The Employment and Decent Work for Peace and Resilience Recommendation (ILO, 2017a) and the Violence and Harassment Convention (ILO, 2019) explicitly target the protection of migrant workers and refugees. Building on these, the Resolution concerning fair and effective labour migration governance (ILO, 2017b), adopted at the 106th Session of the International Labour Conference, established a normative framework for ILO member states. It positioned labor migration governance within the principles of human rights, equality, and social justice, moving beyond a narrow focus on economic efficiency. The resolution guided subsequent ILO action, including the five-year Plan of Action (2017–2022) and the expansion of the Fair Migration Agenda. In 2025, the 353rd Session of the ILO Governing Body further advanced this trajectory through the discussion of “ILO Agenda and Action on Fair Migration” (ILO, 2025). This agenda sets clear priorities for strengthening migrant workers’ rights and institutionalizing rights-based governance of labor migration at the global level.

The full-scale war triggered a massive forced migration of Ukrainians to European countries. The unprecedented activation of the Temporary Protection Directive granted them immediate access to the labor market. This created conditions for a “quasi-natural experiment” (Verme and Schuettler, 2021), enabling the study of the benefits of early labor market integration of migrants—when skills are less eroded and social support is available (Zikic and Klehe, 2021), although employment choices may be less informed and significant language barriers remain (Dahlberg et al., 2022).

Labor markets in European countries are experiencing a shortage of workers and a substantial level of labor market slack (Eurostat, 2024), along with increasing demand for digital and green skills amid technological transformation (International Monetary Fund, 2024). Labor markets are becoming increasingly fragmented, and the gap in labor force participation rates between native workers and migrant workers remains deep (Gonne, 2023). Do migrants help alleviate these issues or exacerbate them, especially amid technological changes? What improvements can be made to migrant labor conditions and compliance with decent work standards while simultaneously addressing labor market bottlenecks? How can migrants help to overcome digital and green skills shortages in fragmented labor markets?

Background: skill loss of migrant workers and labor markets in transformation

Human capital plays a crucial role in shaping high standards of decent work for migrants, facilitating their economic and social integration. Yet significant barriers remain: legal obstacles, including the recognition of skills (Haensel Schmitt et al., 2023), economic constraints and discrimination (Shen et al., 2024), and the pull of informal labor markets (Guild & Barylska, 2021). But what happens when the level of skills development and formal education is either insufficient or mismatched with the labor market requirements of the host country? Or when sudden migration, such as flight from war, precludes any prior labor market assessment and preparatory steps typically associated with deliberate labor migration? In such cases, the expectation–reality gap, already present in planned migration, can deepen further, producing more severe negative consequences (Sbaa et al., 2025).

The working conditions of migrants have become a subject of scholarly attention due to persistent challenges such as poorer labor standards and skill loss. Migrant work frequently falls short of the basic dimensions of decent work—adequate wages, proper social protection, and opportunities for career advancement remain limited (Guild & Barylska, 2021). In certain sectors of the economy, migrants and refugees face the most severe deficits in decent work, while ethnic discrimination remains unresolved (Loosemore et al., 2021). Women migrants are particularly vulnerable with respect to working hours, workload intensity, language barriers, and access to social protection (Pyo & Yang, 2024). As we will show below, several of these vulnerabilities are especially evident among Ukrainian women with children, the majority of those displaced by the war.

Recent research further underscores that phenomena such as deskilling and brain waste are systemic features of migrants' position in the European labor market. A large-scale comparative study across 17 Western European countries (Pricila Birgier & Cantalini, 2024) showed that migrants are significantly more likely than natives to experience a mismatch between their educational attainment and their actual employment. A typical manifestation is overeducation: highly qualified individuals working in positions that do not require their level of skills. As emphasized by Pricila Birgier & Cantalini (2024), the key drivers of this situation include weak language integration, ineffective recognition mechanisms for foreign qualifications, and structural barriers to access professional occupations. At the same time, cross-country variation is evident: in Northern and Western European states with robust integration programs, the scale of skill loss is lower, whereas in Southern Europe, the problem is far greater.

The experience of Ukrainian migrants confirms these patterns at the local level. In a study by Aigner, Korzeniewska, and Nowicka (2024), conducted among highly educated Ukrainian refugee women in Upper Austria and Poland, a significant share of respondents reported skill loss, being forced to take jobs far below their level of education and professional experience. The authors stress that this outcome is not the result of individual characteristics, but rather a consequence of integration practices oriented toward the rapid filling of vacancies in labor-shortage sectors, with little regard for existing human capital. Thus, both strands of evidence point to a common trend: whether in the broad European context or in specific national cases of Ukrainian migrants, the undervaluation of skills remains systemic. This results in the erosion of human potential and reduced opportunities for socio-economic integration, with long-term implications not only for migrants but also for host societies.

Moreover, the structural issue of skill loss gains renewed salience in the context of contemporary economic transformations: the shift toward a “green” and “digital” economy amplifies skill shortages, as demand for new competencies grows much faster than migrants' opportunities to acquire them. Recent research increasingly emphasizes the structural challenges that arise from the twin transitions toward sustainability and digitalization. The demand for new competencies—such as environmental literacy and digital skills—often fails to align with the skill profiles of migrants, deepening the problem of mismatch. Both the European Union and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and

Development (OECD/European Commission, 2024) have expressed the concern that, even where formal employment is secured, migrants remain vulnerable due to limited access to retraining and upskilling opportunities. In parallel, an analysis by the Migration Policy Institute (2025) highlights that the majority of EU residents themselves possess only basic digital skills, while the green and digital transitions are creating strong demand for advanced technical competencies—trends with which immigrants struggle disproportionately. An additional dimension of the digital era highlighted in recent literature concerns data protection and digital rights in the workplace: Zhong and Feng (2025) show that guarantees of digital privacy directly enhance workers' well-being and constitute an integral component of the concept of decent work under conditions of digitalization.

Thus, both classical studies on skill loss and more recent work on green and digital transitions reveal the systemic nature of skill mismatch among migrants. The erosion of human capital not only undermines the individual opportunities of workers but also constrains the potential of host societies—a challenge that becomes especially critical under conditions of growing demand for specialized skills.

Methodology

Between November 2024 and April 2025, a survey was conducted among Ukrainian migrants in three countries: Germany, the Netherlands, and Poland. All Ukrainian migrants in these countries were eligible to participate regardless of the date and purpose of migration or legal status, with the only requirement being prior work experience in the host country. The survey consisted of three sections: an extended demographic module; a block dedicated to decent work and inequality; and a section on the experience of workplace democracy. A substantial share of incomplete responses reduced the volume of usable data. To minimize data loss and preserve sample integrity, imputation procedures for missing values were applied (Van Buuren, 2018).

The entire procedure of preparing the dataset for analysis can be analytically divided into three major steps: data cleaning, categorization and variable construction, and imputation of missing values. This structured approach ensured both the internal consistency of the dataset and the methodological robustness of subsequent statistical analysis.

Data Cleaning

At the initial stage, comprehensive cleaning and harmonization were carried out to ensure data consistency for subsequent imputation. Missing values and logically inconsistent responses were flagged, while erroneous numerical entries were recoded as missing. Range checks were applied: for example, in Likert scales (1–7), values such as “0” or “8” were treated as errors. Categorical variables were standardized to avoid duplication caused by spelling variations or translations. It was observed that missing values were most frequent in questions on working conditions and job satisfaction, while demographic variables were comparatively complete. Open-ended textual responses (comments) were excluded from automated imputation and treated separately as qualitative material.

Categorization and Variable Construction

The next step involved coding open responses and grouping them into standardized categories suitable for quantitative analysis. For instance, mentions of workplace improvements (wages, working hours, social benefits) were consolidated into thematic blocks. For scale-based variables, data were cleaned and harmonized, while related items were integrated into indices (e.g., overall job satisfaction, participation in decision-making), enhancing measurement reliability. Numerical variables were sometimes categorized (e.g., number of dependents, length of employment) to simplify interpretation and ensure

comparability. Variable construction followed logical interdependencies to maintain conceptual validity in subsequent analysis.

Imputation of Missing Values

The final stage was the restoration of missing data, applying a combination of methods depending on variable type. For scale-based variables, iterative imputation (machine learning–based approaches) was employed to capture complex interdependencies and produce more accurate estimates; imputed values were rounded and constrained within permissible ranges. For categorical variables, imputation relied on empirical distributions, filling gaps through random draws that preserved observed frequency patterns. In multidimensional blocks (e.g., assessments of workplace aspects), imputation drew on an extended set of predictors, including demographic characteristics, type of employment, contract form, and interrelated responses within the block.

The accuracy of the results was verified through visualization of comparative distributions, where graphs displayed the relationship between original and imputed values. This approach made it possible to assess whether the chosen method introduced any systematic distortions and to what extent the imputed data reproduced the original structure of the dataset. Ultimately, the combination of regression-based prediction and empirical distribution recovery ensured a comprehensive and balanced imputation strategy, resulting in a complete and reliable dataset for further analysis.

Fig. 1. Distribution of responses for the variable “AspectsOfWork_WorkSchedule” before imputation (blue) and after imputation (orange)

Following the procedures of data cleaning and imputation, the final dataset was established for subsequent analysis. The distribution of respondents after processing was as follows: Germany: 115, Poland: 71, and the Netherlands: 28, amounting to a total of 214 respondents. This distribution broadly corresponds to the actual structure of Ukrainian migrants in these countries. For comparison, the structure of Ukrainian war-displaced persons as of July–August 2025 is presented in Table 1 (UNHCR, 2025).

Table 1

Structure of Ukrainians under temporary protection and survey respondents in selected European countries

Country	Number of Ukrainian migrants (UNHCR)	Survey respondents	UNHCR data reference date
Germany	1233280	115	08/04/2025
Poland	1000240	71	08/12/2025
Netherlands	128150	28	07/31/2025

However, from the perspective of processing survey results, such uneven sample sizes imposed specific requirements on the methods applied, ensuring both relevance and reliable estimates.

Methods applied in processing the data:

- 1) Preliminary exploratory analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to examine the structure of responses across different demographic groups and to compare variations between countries. It should be noted that results for the Netherlands were interpreted with caution due to the relatively small number of respondents. Additionally, analysis of responses to questions beyond decent work enabled the assessment of the match between skills and jobs by gender, age, education, and time of migration. Further insights were obtained regarding the relationship between migrants' current occupations in host countries and their previous professions in the Ukrainian labor market, as well as inequalities between migrants and native workers and the level of workplace democracy experienced by migrants.
- 2) Graphical analysis. Density plots were constructed to visually assess the similarity of response distributions. More precisely, this stage was conducted in parallel with the subsequent application of non-parametric tests, in order to guide decisions on the most appropriate methodological approaches.
- 3) Confirmatory analysis. The objective of this stage was formulated as follows: to identify significant, statistically meaningful differences in indicators of decent work (as perceived by respondents) across the three countries. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) can yield robust results but requires prior assumptions of normal data distribution and homogeneity of variances. In the case of this survey, such assumptions could not be met. Therefore, non-parametric tests—ANOVA equivalents suitable when distributional assumptions are not satisfied—were employed. In certain cases, these tests are the only feasible option to obtain valid results. The survey of migrants presented in this article exemplifies such a case, demanding rigorous methodological handling. Preliminary graphical analysis using density plots revealed clear dissimilarities in response distributions and did not allow for unambiguous conclusions regarding their normality. Moreover, the responses themselves are effectively ordinal in nature, and the sample sizes were markedly unequal (after data cleaning: 28 responses for the Netherlands, 71 for Poland, and 115 for Germany). These characteristics imposed even stricter requirements on the choice of appropriate analytical approaches.

Several non-parametric tests were applied in the study. The primary method employed was the **Kruskal–Wallis test** (Kruskal & Wallis, 1952), which is appropriate for comparing more than two independent samples (Ostertagová, Ostertag, & Kováč, 2014). This test provides more robust results than ANOVA F-tests when the distributional properties of samples are uncertain (Nwobi & Akanno, 2021). It also demonstrates optimal performance when analyzing samples of unequal sizes or differing distributions (Rahrig, 2024). While most studies have applied it without relying on the assumption of normality, Gerald & Patson (2021) raised arguments to the contrary. Moreover, there is evidence, alongside opportunities for further improvement, that rank-based non-parametric tests may achieve greater statistical power than their parametric counterparts (Couch et al., 2019). The Kruskal–Wallis test is designed to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between group medians. The test statistic H is computed as follows:

$$H = \frac{12}{N(N+1)} \sum_{j=1}^k \left(\frac{R_j^2}{n_j} \right) - 3(N+1),$$

where R_j – denotes the rank sum of the j group,

$$N = \sum_{j=1}^k n_j$$

k is the number of groups, n_j – is the number of observations in the j group (Kruskal & Wallis, 1952).

Prior to computation, two hypotheses are formulated: H_0 – all groups share the same distribution:

$$F_1(x) = F_2(x) = \dots = F_k(x) \text{ for each } x.$$

Alternative hypothesis H_1 : at least one group differs: i.e., there exist $i \neq j$ such that $F_i(x) \neq F_j(x)$ for some x , in other words, at least one average rank is different, and the distributions are not identical.

The Kruskal–Wallis tests were applied to items measured on Likert scales. However, the Kruskal–Wallis test does not provide information about which specific country groups differ. Moreover, the relatively small sample size for the Netherlands may reduce the statistical power of the test. The Kruskal–Wallis procedure is omnibus in nature—if a significant difference is detected among groups, post-hoc tests (pairwise comparisons) are required to determine which groups differ. For our Likert-type data, the Brunner–Munzel test with Holm correction was selected as the primary post-hoc approach. This choice increases the robustness of the results without assuming equal distributions.

Strictly speaking, the Brunner–Munzel test is not a post-hoc method, as it was originally designed as an alternative to the Mann–Whitney test without the assumption of identical distributions.

Nevertheless, when more than two groups are involved, the Brunner–Munzel test can be used post-hoc by performing all pairwise comparisons between groups with a multiple-testing correction (Holm, in this study).

Justification for the choice of the Brunner–Munzel test. The main limitation of non-parametric tests for multiple samples lies in the asymmetry of distributions. While the Mann–Whitney–Wilcoxon test is widely used, it does not account for heteroscedasticity and suffers from restricted statistical power. In particular, its assumption of identical distributions is not satisfied in our dataset. For this reason, testing the hypothesis of stochastic equality is more meaningful, as it evaluates the probability of dominance between groups. In the context of survey results, this can be formulated as follows: *what is the probability that the position of Ukrainian migrants in terms of decent work is better in one country than in another?*

Accordingly, the application of the Brunner–Munzel test in this study yields conclusions about both the presence and magnitude of the probability that one group (Ukrainian migrants in a given country) dominates another with respect to different dimensions of decent work. In this research, it was employed as a post-hoc test for pairwise comparisons between the three countries. The test is robust to differences in distributional shape and heteroscedasticity and explicitly examines the stochastic superiority of one group over another.

Two independent samples are considered $n_1 (X_{11}, \dots, X_{1n_1})$, and $n_2 (X_{21}, \dots, X_{2n_2})$:

$$X_{ik} \sim F_i$$

$i = 1, 2, k = 1, \dots, n_i$.

N – total number of observations $N = n_1 + n_2$.

The null hypothesis is formulated as stochastic equality between the two samples:

$H_0: \hat{p} = 0.5$, де \hat{p} – the stochastic dominance statistic:

$$\hat{p} = P(X_{11} > X_{21}) + \frac{1}{2} P(X_{11} = X_{21})$$

is estimated as the proportion of “wins” across all possible pairs (with half weight assigned to ties). It implies that neither group tends to have higher values than the other, and thus the distributions exhibit stochastic equality.

The alternative hypothesis:

$H_1: \hat{p} \neq 0.5$ – states that values from one group are more likely to be larger than those from the other.

To test these hypotheses, the Brunner–Munzel statistic W_N^{BF} is employed, which is calculated as follows:

$$W_N^{BF} = \frac{\sqrt{N}(\hat{p} - \frac{1}{2})}{\hat{\sigma}_N} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \cdot \frac{\bar{R}_2 - \bar{R}_1}{\hat{\sigma}_N}$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_N^2 = N \cdot \left[\frac{\hat{\sigma}_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\hat{\sigma}_2^2}{n_2} \right]$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_1^2$ and $\hat{\sigma}_2^2$ – variance estimation for two samples

Fagerland et al. (2011) argue that for samples smaller than 10 observations, the Brunner–Munzel test performs poorly, while other sources (Neubert & Brunner, 2007) indicate that the test remains applicable in such cases provided that permutation procedures are employed.

When pairwise comparisons are conducted across more than two groups, the probability of Type I errors increases, necessitating the use of multiple-testing corrections. Given the unequal sample sizes and distributional differences in our data, Holm’s step-down correction was applied (Lydersen, 2024). Effect size is a critical indicator for the comprehensive interpretation of non-parametric test results. It is often more substantively meaningful than the simple probability of statistical significance (the p-value in statistical tests) (Coe, 2002). *Effect size* demonstrates the magnitude of differences between two groups when testing hypotheses about medians, means, or distributions.

In this study, the task was to determine the stochastic dominance of one group over another; therefore, the effect size was evaluated using the Vargha–Delaney statistic (*A12*) (Vargha & Delaney, 2000). A value of 0.5 indicates no dominance; >0.5 — indicate dominance of Group 1, <0.5 — indicate dominance of Group 2. For interpretative clarity, commonly applied thresholds of effect size were used: trivial ≈ 0.54 , small ≈ 0.56 , medium ≈ 0.64 , large ≈ 0.71 . When expressed symmetrically around 0.5:

$0.44 \leq A12 \leq 0.56 \rightarrow$ trivial effect

$0.36 \leq A12 < 0.44$ OR $0.56 < A12 \leq 0.64 \rightarrow$ small effect

$0.29 \leq A12 < 0.36$ OR $0.64 < A12 \leq 0.71 \rightarrow$ medium effect

$A12 < 0.29$ OR $A12 > 0.71 \rightarrow$ large effect (Vargha & Delaney, 2000)

The calculations were carried out in R using the function *effsize::VD.A*, which returns the estimate of *A* (Torchiano, 2020).

All computations were performed in the RStudio environment (Mangiafico, 2016; Kruskal–Wallis Test R Documentation; Toshiaki, 2022). In R, both the asymptotic p-value and the permutation-based p-value are implemented in the *brunnermunzel* package (options *asym=TRUE* and *perm=TRUE*).

The sequence of non-parametric testing procedures in R included the following steps:

- loading the required packages and libraries;
- defining the dependent variable (“country”) and the independent variables; (characteristics of decent work among migrants) ;
- cleaning and recoding scale values: (1) identifying best and worst ratings through rank assignment, with careful treatment of reverse-coded questions (where “1” may represent either the best or worst value); (2) replacing responses without ordinal meaning (e.g., “Hard to say,” “I don’t know,” “Prefer not to say”) with NA; (3) reversing the coding of inverted scales where necessary;
- performing computational procedures for test statistics, p-values, adjusted p-values, effect sizes, and other relevant parameters;
- exporting and saving the results into separate files.

Results

The ILO’s Manual on Decent Work Indicators (ILO, 2013) identifies ten substantive elements for measuring decent work, reflecting the four strategic pillars of the decent work concept: employment opportunities; adequate earnings and productive work; decent working time; reconciliation of work, family and personal life; elimination of work that should not exist; stability and security of work; equal opportunity and treatment in employment; safe working environment; social security; and social dialogue, including workers’ and employers’ representation.

The European Working Conditions Surveys (EWCS) evaluate job quality across seven main dimensions: physical environment, work intensity, working time quality, social environment, skills and discretion, earnings, and prospects (Eurofound, 2024).

To capture these aspects of decent work and job quality as comprehensively as possible within a survey framework, a set of targeted questions was included in the questionnaire (Table 2). Respondents were asked to evaluate statements about their current (or most recent) workplace: “To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your current (last) workplace?” with responses ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree / not at all correct) to 5 (Strongly agree / completely correct). All responses such as “Hard to say” and “I do not want to answer the question” were excluded from the analysis, as they carry no substantive meaning in the applied methodological framework.

Table 2

Alignment of the questionnaire with decent work dimensions and job quality characteristics

Statement in the questionnaire (To what extent do you agree with the following statements about your current (last) workplace?)	Abbreviation (for ease of reference in results)	Decent work dimensions (ILO, 2013)	Job quality characteristics (EWCS) (Eurofound, 2017)
I am familiar with the official documents that regulate my work (e.g. job instructions, collective agreements, labor contract, work schedule, occupational health and safety instructions, etc.)	Familiar_documents	safe work environment	Physical environment
I feel physically safe at my job	Feel_safe	safe work environment	Physical environment
In case of an emergency involving a workplace hazard, I know what to do or where to find relevant instructions/guides	Ready_case_hazard	safe work environment	Physical environment
I can take paid sick-leave when necessary	Sick_leave	work that should be abolished; employment opportunities; social security	Working time quality Social environment
I can choose my work schedule	Choose_workschedule	decent working time	Working time quality
I can choose between offline and online work (from the workplace or from home)	Choose_off_online	decent working time combining work, family and personal life	Working time quality
I can plan my working time ahead	Plan_worktime	decent working time combining work, family and personal life	Working time quality
I am satisfied with the duration of my working time (shift time) per day	Duration_worktime	decent working time combining work, family and personal life	Working time quality
Sometimes I have to work unpaid overtime	Work_unpaid_overtime	work that should be abolished	Working time quality Earnings
I have a decent salary, which allows me to feel confident	Decent_salary	adequate earnings and productive work	Earnings

My work allows me to spend enough time with children, family and for household and leisure	Enough_time_family	combining work, family and personal life	Working time quality
I can express dissatisfaction with the working conditions, its organization, etc. to the employer/head of my department	Can_express_dissatisfaction	Social dialogue, workers' and employers' representation	Social environment
There is no compulsion to work overtime against my will	Work_overtime_against_will	stability and security of work	Work intensity
I was not forced to do additional work that did not correspond to the scope or content of my job description	Additional_work	work that should be abolished	Work intensity Social environment
I am in a constant stress at my work	Constant_stress	stability and security of work	Work intensity
My job involves periodic revision of wages	Revision_wages	adequate earnings and productive work	Earnings Prospects
There are possibilities for career growth	Career_growth	Employment opportunities	Skills and discretion Prospects
If I want, I can participate in advanced training courses to improve my qualification	Participate_training	Employment opportunities	Skills and discretion Prospects
There are additional rewards, benefits, bonuses (e.g., free travel to work, accommodation, meals (lunches), health insurance, reimbursement of mobile phone costs by the employer, etc.)	Social_rewards	Social security	Social environment

Exploratory data analysis was conducted to compare the variation in responses across countries. Median values, standard deviations, quartiles, interquartile ranges (IQR), and low and high whiskers were calculated. The analysis produced the following results: The largest variation in medians (a gap of 2 on the 1–5 Likert scale) was observed for the indicator “Social_rewards”, with the lowest median response in Germany and the highest in Poland (4). In other words, the median gap of 2 represents the greatest disparity in the dataset. Median gaps of size 1 were observed for most indicators, except for “Feel_safe”, “Ready_case_hazard”, “Sick_leave”, “Plan_worktime”, “Duration_worktime”, “Decent_salary”, and “Work_overtime_against_will”. However, these items displayed other forms of variability. For instance, a substantial interquartile range (IQR) was found in responses to “Plan_worktime” (average 2.75; Netherlands 3.25; Poland 3.0), “Work_overtime_against_will” (outliers in the Netherlands), and “Sick_leave” (outliers present). By contrast, responses regarding “Duration_worktime” showed relative homogeneity.

These findings provided the basis for advancing the analysis using non-parametric testing (See Appendix). Thus, the Kruskal–Wallis test indicated statistically significant differences across the three countries in respondents' answers concerning: flexibility in choosing working hours; the possibility of working on-site or remotely; career advancement opportunities; and the availability of additional rewards, benefits, and bonuses (with the null hypothesis rejected at the 0.05 significance level). Under less strict criteria (significance level of 0.1), statistically significant differences were also found in relation to sick leave entitlements and the requirement to work overtime without compensation.

The next step involved conducting post-hoc pairwise comparisons using the Brunner–Munzel test. The results of these procedures are presented in Table 3, which reports only those indicators where statistical significance was observed and highlights the specific differences between countries.

Table 3

Results of the Brunner–Munzel test for selected decent work indicators

Decent work indicator, countries compared, sample size used in the test	bm_ statistic	p_perm (p permutation)	p_asym (p asymptotic)	p_adj_holm (correction Holm)	A12 (effect of size)	Note
Sick leave						
Germany (110) – Poland (68)	-2.097	0.0403	0.0383	0.1209	0.580	Difference not confirmed, no effect
Choose workschedule						
Germany (112) – the Netherlands (27)	2.100	0.0410	0.0426	0.0820	0.371	Small effect, Group 2 advantage (Netherlands)
Germany (112) – Poland (70)	2.407	0.0168	0.0174	0.0504	0.396	Borderline significance (Holm correction at threshold level), small effect, Group 2 advantage (Poland)
Choose off online						
Germany (112) – Poland (70)	2.359	0.0189	0.0198	0.0567	0.403	Borderline significance (Holm correction slightly above threshold), small effect, Group 2 advantage (Poland)
Work unpaid overtime						
Germany (109) - the Netherlands (28)	2.375	0.0273	0.0223	0.0819	0.372	Borderline significance (significance disappears after Holm correction), small effect, Group 2 advantage (Netherlands)
Additional work						
Germany (111) - the Netherlands (28)	2.096	0.0434	0.0417	0.1302	0.389	Difference not confirmed, no effect
Constant stress						
Germany (114) – Poland (69)	2.020	0.0425	0.0451	0.1275	0.417	Difference not confirmed, no effect
Career growth						
Germany (105) – Poland (69)	2.905	0.0050	0.0043	0.0150	0.374	Small effect, Group 2 advantage (Poland)
Social rewards						
Germany (112) – Poland (68)	2.772	0.0060	0.0065	0.0180	0.378	Small effect, Group 2 advantage (Poland)

* - statistically significant differences between countries are highlighted in bold italics

Interpretation of results

The bm statistic by itself has little substantive meaning, as it only serves as the basis for calculating p-values. The main indicators of group differences are p-asymptotic, p-permutation, and p-adjust Holm. When these values are below 0.05, the differences between countries can be considered statistically significant.

Comparison of the Kruskal–Wollis and Brunner–Munzel test results are provided in the table 4.

Table 4

Comparison of the Kruskal–Wallis and Brunner–Munzel test results on the assessment of decent work dimensions among migrants

Decent work indicator	Differentiation according to Kruskal-Wallis test	Differentiation according to Brunner–Munzel test
Sick leave	+	-
Choose workschedule	+	+
Choose off online	+	+
Work unpaid overtime	+	+
Additional work	-	-
Constant stress	-	-
Career growth	+	+
Social rewards	+	+

The differences between countries concern the following aspects:

- (1) Opportunities to choose and plan work schedules, including remote work. Germany shows more limited opportunities in this regard: ~62.9% of respondents in the Netherlands and ~60.4% in Poland report greater freedom in planning their working hours. In addition, about ~59.7% of Ukrainians in Poland rated their chances of choosing between online and on-site work higher than in Germany.
- (2) Opportunities for career advancement. Around ~62.8% of respondents in Poland reported seeing greater prospects for themselves compared to Ukrainians in Germany.
- (3) Access to additional bonuses, social packages, and benefits. This dimension of decent work revealed the most significant difference according to the Kruskal–Wallis test. The difference was also confirmed by the Brunner–Munzel test, albeit with a small effect: approximately ~62.2% of respondents in Poland indicated having greater opportunities to receive such benefits.
- (4) Borderline significant differences were observed with respect to forced overtime without additional pay.

Overall, the differences identified (in terms of effect size) are not substantial (Table 3), yet they do exist and warrant deeper investigation. An important characteristic of the sample is that respondents in Germany have, on average, the longest duration of stay: nearly 20% have been in the country for more than five years (compared to 15% in Poland and 7% in the Netherlands). This implies that migrants in Germany had more time to secure better employment and improve their language proficiency (Fig. 2). At the same time, high standards of social protection and assistance available to Ukrainians under temporary protection in Germany may also play an important role—although this category of migrants has typically spent less than five years abroad.

Fig. 2. Duration of stay of respondents in host countries

As noted, the questionnaire also covered many other aspects of migrants’ engagement in the labor market. These included issues of skills mismatch and loss of employment status, the adequacy of skills relative to current jobs, and inequalities between Ukrainian migrants, native workers, and migrants from other countries. It should be emphasized that results for the Netherlands must be interpreted with caution due to the relatively small number of responses.

Skills (mis)match

Findings on skill mismatch and the navigation of acquired educational skills were derived from the question: “Does your current (or most recent) job match your abilities and skills?” The highest share of full skill–job match was observed in Poland—45.1% of respondents (Fig. 3). This may reflect either effective job–qualification matching or lower expectations regarding adequacy. By contrast, the Netherlands reported the lowest rates, particularly among middle-aged respondents (35–54) and men. Overall, individuals aged 56+ displayed the weakest results across all three countries. Among younger respondents (15–34), higher levels of skill–job matching were found in Germany and Poland (7.5 and 9.9 percentage points above the overall average, respectively), whereas in the Netherlands the trend was reversed. Nevertheless, 37.8% of young people (below 35 years old) in Poland reported either having to acquire new skills or working in positions below their level of ability. This suggests a greater diversity of experiences among respondents in Poland.

Fig. 3. Skill–job match among respondents (distribution of answers to the question) “Do you think that your current (last) main job meets (met) your abilities and skills?”

By educational attainment, the highest share of **underutilization of skills** was observed among respondents with a bachelor’s degree: 42.4% reported that their job was below their level of skills and abilities—the highest rate among all education groups. In contrast, those with a master’s or doctoral degree most frequently indicated a full match between their skills and job requirements. The least satisfied group consisted of individuals with secondary, incomplete secondary, or other types of education. Respondents with vocational education more often stated that they had to acquire new skills. Across occupational sectors, the picture is similarly nuanced. In education, science, and research, only 50% of respondents reported a full skill–job match; one quarter indicated a partial match; 11.5% had to acquire new skills and knowledge (possibly language-related); and an equal share reported being overqualified for their current positions. The latter responses were especially common in Germany (18.5%) and the Netherlands (16.7%). In ICT, the situation was more favourable, particularly in Poland, where 57% of respondents reported a full match. By contrast, in Germany the distribution was more fragmented: about one-third had to improve their skills, while another third either acquired new skills or continued to work in positions below their qualification level.

An important question addressed in the study was the impact of early labor market integration of migrants. The distribution of responses concerning the skill–job match by country is presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Distribution of responses on skill–job match by country

Data in Figure 4 illustrate a higher level of skill–job matching among those who had more time to integrate into the labor market, i.e., those who arrived before the outbreak of the full-scale war in 2022 and made a more deliberate and prepared choice. Certain patterns are nevertheless noteworthy. Among those who migrated after the start of the full-scale war, the share of respondents working below their skill level is higher in Germany and the Netherlands compared to the overall migrant population. By contrast, in Poland this group shows distinctly better outcomes: significantly more responses of “Yes, absolutely” and “Yes, partially” regarding skill–job match, which may be considered a positive trend for recent arrivals. Moreover, in Poland new migrants with only partial skill matches appear more willing to accept such jobs. Clearly, the language barrier plays an important role here, being significantly lower in Poland, particularly for those who speak Ukrainian (rather than Russian).

The distribution of responses on skill–job match by employment field is presented in Figure 5. This distribution corresponds to the patterns observed by educational attainment: higher skill–job matching is more evident in sectors where educational requirements are greater.

Fig. 5. Distribution of responses on skill–job match by employment sector

An analysis of respondents’ answers to the question “Is (Was) your current (last) main job professionally related to the work which you had in Ukraine?” (Fig. 6), taking into account gender, age, and education, provides insights into the patterns of **cross-border transferability of professional skills**. More than one-third (34.6%) of respondents reported that their current (or most recent) job fully matched their previous professional experience in Ukraine, 18.2% indicated a partial continuation of the same activity, while 40.7% reported working in a completely different field unrelated to their prior experience. Men were more likely than women to fully continue their professional activity: 50.9% compared to 28.8%, which may be associated with men’s longer average duration of stay in host countries. Respondents aged 35–54 appeared the most stable in terms of professional continuity, while younger respondents were more likely to change fields of employment. Poland demonstrated the highest level of full professional match (53.5% overall), while the Netherlands showed the highest level of mismatch (57.1%) (Fig. 6). Respondents with a master’s or doctoral degree were most likely to maintain full professional continuity (39.7%), whereas those with a bachelor’s degree exhibited the greatest level of occupational disintegration, with 66.7% working in jobs unrelated to their previous employment in Ukraine. By country, the distribution of mismatch among bachelor’s degree holders was: Germany – 63.2%, the Netherlands – 88.9%, and Poland – 40.0%.

Fig.6. Correspondence between current job and previous professional experience (Distribution of responses to the question: “Is (Was) your current (last) main job professionally related to the work which you had in Ukraine?”)

Remote work. Among the 25 respondents working remotely, 14 were located in Poland. The majority of remote workers were employed in Education, Science, and Research (primarily in Germany, fewer in Poland), as well as in Information and Communication Technologies (mostly in Poland). Notably, more than 70% of respondents working remotely in Germany and the Netherlands reported that their skills fully matched the requirements of their current jobs, whereas 42% of remote workers in Poland indicated that they had to improve their skills. This suggests that Ukrainians migrating westward with remote contracts make more deliberate employment choices, while in neighbouring countries migrants are more likely to rely on opportunities for retraining, adaptation, or approximate skill matching. At the same time, this dynamic may reinforce fragmentation within local labor markets.

Conclusion and discussion

Overall, the study covers a broad range of issues related to the labor market engagement of Ukrainian migrants and the extent to which decent work standards are upheld. The survey results were characterized by unequal sample sizes and asymmetric, heterogeneous distributions of responses to certain questions. For this reason, non-parametric tests were employed in assessing dimensions of decent work. Based on the results, the most pronounced differences in the situation of Ukrainians across the three countries—Netherlands, Germany, and Poland—concern decent working time and the planning of work schedules, access to social benefits, and career advancement opportunities. The more regulated the labor market, the more difficult it becomes for migrants to adapt to it and to find employment that is both decent and adequately matched to their skills and education. Language barriers remain high, highlighting the need for appropriate policy responses from labor market regulatory bodies.

The Polish labor market integrates newly arrived migrants more rapidly and makes fuller use of their skills and previous professional experience, primarily due to lower language barriers. Poland is also characterized by less regulated labor market structures and, arguably, a higher prevalence of informal employment. Therefore, rapid integration into the labor market cannot always be assessed unambiguously as a positive outcome. Greater labor market regulation has its advantages, particularly in terms of enhanced social protection.

All countries share an interest in improving skill navigation – both migrants and host societies benefit—especially under conditions of technological change, increasing fragmentation of European labor markets, shortages of green and digital skills, and labor market stagnation. Migrants represent an important source of labor supply. However, individuals without formal education, as well as those with bachelor’s degrees, are more vulnerable on the labor market. By contrast, respondents with master’s or doctoral degrees were more likely to maintain full professional continuity, while bachelor’s degree holders showed the highest levels of occupational disintegration. The institutionalization of skill navigation pathways—through better job-matching mechanisms, improved access to retraining and micro-qualification services, and the reduction of regulatory barriers to migrant employment—could help address local labor market deficits and strengthen decent work opportunities for migrants in the context of ongoing technological transformations.

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Results of the Kruskal–Wallis test for decent work indicators among Ukrainian migrants in the Netherlands, Germany, and Poland

Decent work indicator	Kruskal test H	p-value
Familiar documents	1,4158	0,4927
Feel safe	1,1380	0,5661
Ready case hazard	1,5684	0,4565
Sick leave	4,8657**	0,0878
Choose workschedule	8,0853***	0,0176
Choose off online	5,7767***	0,0557
Plan worktime	1,1443	0,5643
Duration worktime	0,4456	0,8003
Work unpaid overtime	5,1351**	0,0767
Decent salary	1,1450	0,5641
Enough time family	2,7652	0,2509
Can express dissatisfaction	1,9585	0,3756
Work overtime against will	0,9913	0,6092
Additional work	3,5809	0,1669
Constant stress	3,8967	0,1425
Revision wages	0,8340	0,6590
Career growth	8,3577***	0,0153
Participate training	3,2050	0,2014
Social rewards	7,8002***	0,0202

** - H_0 can be rejected at the 0.1 significance level, indicating differences between countries

*** - H_0 can be rejected at the 0.05 significance level, indicating stronger evidence of differences between countries